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SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT AND EQUITY IN INDONESIA

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ADIWIDYA 9 | #SINERGIKANPERAN
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The New Strategy Schizophrenia's Services for Indonesia

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Abstract. Indonesia ranks fourth of the world's population. This situation becomes a challenge to provide basic needs such as public health. On the other hand, in reality people with mental illness in part who are locked up, shackled and thrown away. This is way until now, they are not have received optimal mental health service. Subsequently, schizophrenia have negative stigma and discrimination makes they needs are ignored. Accordingly, it is important to give more attention and empower those who need medical and rehabilitation. Therefore, systematic literature review talks about the concepts, Indonesia's problem services and digital service function. Finally, this paper has some suggestion for making positive change with collaborative governance. So, everyone can contribute via integrated information system as soon as possible for smart people in Indonesia.

Keywords: Mental Illness, Schizophrenia, Public Health Service, Collaborative Governance, Indonesia

1. Introduction

Indonesia as a developing country whose population is spread from Sabang to Merauke. One other thing, 273. 523.621 million people in Indonesia is the fourth largest population for all countries [1,2]. So, health services then become one of the issues that need attention. We must to remember, human not only need physical health but also mental health is important too. In this situation need some program with very creative to manage patient mental illness when Covid-19 pandemic for example schizophrenia. Generally, people with serious mental illness have low immunity because brain dysfunction [3]. They are necessary the good quality of life every single day from virus with providing mental health care. Different from reality, talk about people with schizophrenia until now the others still give negative perception [4,5]. Subsequently, they are unhealthy hence depression for long term and discrimination on social network for them [6]. The inherent efforts to change people with schizophrenia require optimal support for psychosocial interventions [7,8]. This is way, attention extra treatment can be challenging for to control schizophrenia like inpatient care [9]. Since 2013 and 2018, cases of schizophrenia in Indonesia have been increasing. The prevalence is 11.0 per mile in the population groups recorded in rural and urban areas. Suffering due to shackles, not taking medicine or not being able to buy medicine [10,11]. Moreover, this situation is urgent and innovative strategies must to improve on decision making for problem solving [12]. Furthermore, based on the literature review in middle-income countries, access to health services for schizophrenia has not become a priority. Difficulties in accessing health services and budget allocation are a problem [13,14]. Health basic must to present and keep on priorities agenda [15]. For all of those reasons, strategy program with following public can make for success in the new

project. Collaborative governance can interventions for treatment for rehabilitation services with support policy from Government and then to improve positive thinking with shared understanding, people with Schizophrenia can raise again for empower themselves [16]. Admittedly Malaysia condition, in there also need support of economic health service due to Government and other people to help patient [17]. Certainly, Indonesia need new design from research agenda for improving provide financial to help any person with Schizophrenia in Indonesia.

2. Methodology

In this article, to describe qualitative with narrative review for guide understanding the concept and then answered research question. There is elaboration of articles that support the conclusion. The overall argument that is accommodated for developing in the future planning. Identically systematic literature review method can be used to explain this problem and gaps. In this knowledge, process literature review began from the research question, search any articles relevant of the issues, analyze and report data [18]. Important for to know, articles for reference should be good quality and consistent about mental illness with valid data [19]. Reference sources from international journals and non-English language articles are used in the statement of this article. We were to limitation of period articles published in the eleven years ago (from date 2010 until 2021). Combination of three keywords with schizophrenia, public health services and then public administration reform can help in focusing framework. Then, literature review was using information from website include many reports Government of Indonesia and also reputable journal citation. Scopus and Science Direct, we are using for support database articles published. First, 206.634 articles at Scopus database and after filtering section 17 journal articles can be used. Second, we are seen 192.993 journal articles and then choose 12 journal articles from Science Direct database. So, this social study used 29 articles from journal talk about schizophrenia with eliminating process.

3. Result and Discussion

In Indonesia, there are still individuals with schizophrenia who are shackled or abandoned on the streets. Even though the correct treatment is through family interaction assisted by the handling of medical personnel for therapy [20,21,22]. Recovery can be accelerated by caring for the any community who contribute the cost funding during the pharmacological process in clinic [23]. Furthermore, cooperation then becomes the main foundation in recovery as part of the needs of humans with mental illness. This perspective of good governance is expected to form a new group to work together to deal with public issues. Collaborative governance theory is used in social research as an analytical tool to find new services to help schizophrenia. The theory comes from articles related to collaborative governance that have a supportive impact with social processes. Additionally collaborative governance as a concept that public dialogue and mutual commitment can be realize. Public trust and participation are carried out to achieve optimal achievement [24,25,26]. Moreover, according to Crosby and Bryson, the explanation on the concept related to the collaborative governance is controlled in context of the public system [27]. It can be interpreted that the collaboration process runs dynamically because it sees the principles that are bound between during decision making and implementation. This method then provides the motivation that drives them to take action. So, the capacity of stakeholders can be seen after the action and adaptation. The participation of many actors will help in improving mental illness services for recovery of patients. A case study in China proved that mental illness related programs could be promoted to get public attention [28]. Literacy about mental illness in Indonesia give more attention to get some help the caregiver from any social welfare worker and also material they are needs [29,30]. However, low-cost health services need to be implemented to accommodate every schizophrenia patient [31,32]. Therefore, the innovation of Glenn J. Treisman et.al., provide good idea that the use of technology in applications is needed to facilitate reporting, volunteering, financing, and patient health information progress [33]. Finally, application Wecan.com (Kitabisa.com) in Indonesia can be as team work to support, persuade and suggestion the citizen for help people with schizophrenia to be empower for their own lives in the future. Innovation must to be enter formulation policy to better life in Indonesia.

4. Conclusion

The fourth largest population of Indonesia in the world, its mean they are needs to be supported by easy of public services include mental health. People with serious mental illness such as schizophrenia need to get more attention from the public. This is important to make optimal recovery through inpatient care and medication. Moreover, everyone can help provide financial assistance for the treatment of schizophrenia patients in mental hospitals or foundations engaged focus on mental health. Cooperation between the government, foundation owners and the community including relatives can be connected in applications such as Wecan.com (*Kitabisa.com*) on gadgets to platform their assistance. It is hoped that problems related to the cost of mental health services in Indonesia can be accommodated by the assistance of the Government and the community towards a smart people in Indonesia.

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